

Synthesis of users' demands for scenario application and benchmarking tool for UF-NBS (Milestone 4.3)

REFERENCE AS

Wolff, M.; Scheuer, S.; Haase, D. (2021): Synthesis of users' demands for scenario application and benchmarking tool for UF-NBS. Milestone 4.3: Workshop synthesising users' demands for application and benchmarking tool conducted. H2020 project CLEARING HOUSE, grant agreement no. 821242. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10732478

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction and objective	2
1.1	Task description	2
1.2	Screening user demands	2
2	Demands defined by stakeholders and key users for the scenario application for UF-NBS	5
2.1	Objectives	5
2.2	Functionality	5
2.3	Integration	6
3	Demands defined by stakeholders and key users for the benchmarking tool for UF-NBS	6
3.1	Objectives	6
3.2	Functionality	7
3.3	Integration	7
	References	8

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In order to take into account the demands defined by stakeholders and key users in the co-design process, and by the user advisory, an inception workshop was organised connected to the Sino-European co-design event in 2021. Thereby, the objectives, functionality, and integration of two tools to be developed under Task 4.2 have been discussed and defined by the consortium partners and external stakeholders (including the user advisory group).

Synthesis of users' demands for scenario application and benchmarking tool for UF-NBS (Milestone 4.3)

1 Introduction and objective

1.1 Task description

This task will include the development and testing of distinct decision support tools for facilitating the deployment of UFBS in light of the knowledge generated by CLEARING HOUSE. The decision support tools include:

- an (online) **scenario application** for developing, modelling and assessing UFBS scenarios in urban development with the aim to optimise UFBS for cost-effective and performant service delivery at diverging scales. The scenario development will be based on remote sensing and GIS data and will primarily use a rulebased method that translates expert-knowledge into patterns – change in land-use, forest stand and tree density – for iterative time steps. This novel approach to UFBS deployment and urban planning will also be used for the citizen science task as well as communication and dissemination.
- a simple but effective global **benchmarking tool** to compare UFBS in different settings. The benchmark will assess structure and design of UFBS, and their environmental, ecological, economic and social impacts. The benchmarking tool is not only to be used for comparing different UFBS in different locations, but will also be useful for assessing single UFBS during their planning and design phases (“quick scan”). The benchmarking tool will be closely linked with IUCN’s Global Standard on Nature-Based Solutions for Societal Challenges (IUCN, 2020).

1.2 Screening user demands

This task takes into account the demands defined by stakeholders and key users in the co-design process, and by the user advisory group. After setting-up a mockup-template for both tools potential users are closely involved in the development of the benchmarking tool through a users’ evaluation.

Synthesis of users' demands for scenario application and benchmarking tool for UF-NBS (Milestone 4.3)

A kick-off event of the working group on 30.04.2021 already identified the following key users and stakeholders for the two tools:

Scenario application	Benchmarking tool
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Urban planners ▪ Municipal officials ▪ City organisations ▪ Companies that focus on urban (greenspace) planning and management ▪ Certain sectors that own land and benefit most from UF - schools and tourism ▪ Activists, NGOs, campaigners ▪ Educators training urban professionals in Universities ▪ Urbanists ▪ Research / academia ▪ General public ▪ Citizens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Urban initiatives and collectives that span multiple cities e.g. Olympic Committee, city partnerships, World Bank Resilient green cities ▪ Donors and investors into sustainable development ▪ Consulting firms commissioned by local authorities in strategy development ▪ Research / academia

Within an inception workshop connected to the Sino-European co-design event (25.06.2021) the terms for further decision support development have been defined by the consortium partners and external stakeholders (Figure 1). The demand was structured along the following three questions which will be presented in detail in chapter 3:

- (1) Objectives:** What are your knowledge gaps (what challenges do you face and what do you want to know about them)?
- (2) Functionality:** How should the tool be designed, what functions do you wish, how professional should it be or how can it be integrated with something you already know?
- (3) Integration:** How would you like the results look like so that you can actually use them for planning, supporting decisions, convince residents etc.?

Synthesis of users' demands for scenario application and benchmarking tool for UF-NBS (Milestone 4.3)

2 Demands defined by stakeholders and key users for the scenario application for UF-NBS

2.1 Objectives

What are your knowledge gaps (what challenges do you face and what do you want to know about them)?

Scope	Demand for thematic objectives	Demand for technical objectives
NBS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> comparisons of challenges (e.g. floods, storms potential in future) and how NBS can contribute 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the real contribution for specific ES (eg. mitigate the heat waves, improve the air quality) value in money of all the ecosystem services that nature provides in cities
Land Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the relationship between urban grey buildings and green spaces 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> numerical and visual explanation of how the city with forests (trees) differs from the one without + the consequences instruments available for mapping urban land surfaces
Time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> time-scale (how long NBS lasts, but also how long does it take that they fulfil their potential) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> using models to compare past present and future
Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> awareness of what NBS are - that is more general but important Role models - examples of good practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> make sure scientific knowledge reach the policy makers establishing links between scenarios and the "world of the target groups" clear & advanced indicators on NBS

2.2 Functionality

How should the tool be designed, what functions do you wish, how professional should it be or how can it be integrated with something you already know?

Scope	Demand for functionality
NBS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The simulation evaluates the ecosystem services of urban forests Cost effectiveness of different scenarios
Land Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to what extent is it possible to make the tools universal? Taking into account varied conditions in different cities address local spatial planning priorities - relevant to issues that may not occur elsewhere - perhaps suggest a menu approach
Time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> scenarios should be clearly defined (what is a scenario, how can scenarios be described) Good examples how to describe scenarios describe the possible changes in the future including no action
Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> guide for innovative urban planning, stakeholders mapping outcomes (figure or table or graphic pic) should be clear and easy to understand, especially for the group without professional background

Synthesis of users' demands for scenario application and benchmarking tool for UF-NBS (Milestone 4.3)

2.3 Integration

How would you like the results look like so that you can actually use them for planning, supporting decisions, convince residents etc.?

Scope	<i>Demand for integration</i>
NBS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Graphics that are simple to understand the advantages of UF-NBS
Land Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ locally specific - as much as possible (at least on level of our cases) ▪ case studies with "proof" of results
Time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ the language should be very easy understandable; links to studies and further going reports could be given
Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ designed for decision makers rather than technocrats (these generally have no power) ▪ clear principles; may be even some "minimal standards" of good practice

3 Demands defined by stakeholders and key users for the benchmarking tool for UF-NBS

3.1 Objectives

What are your knowledge gaps (what challenges do you face and what do you want to know about them)?

Scope	<i>Demand for thematic objectives</i>	<i>Demand for technical objectives</i>
Comparison	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ how to create the tools for multiple needs (the demands vary cities) ▪ How 'realistic' is 'global' and actually is it desirable as most NBS are local in nature and impact ▪ How do you take into account the differences between cities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ criteria/indicators of NBS contributions ▪ Comprehensive view vs. Details
Explanation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ How to know what is a strong NbS for UF-NBS specifically (IUCN Global Standard for NbS) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 10 key indicators of sustainable NBS ▪ Soft facts as well as hard facts i.e. wellfullness, wellbeing index etc. ▪ Platform of platforms: platform linking all existing platforms with monitoring, research programs etc.

Synthesis of users' demands for scenario application and benchmarking tool for UF-NBS (Milestone 4.3)

3.2 Functionality

How should the tool be designed, what functions do you wish, how professional should it be or how can it be integrated with something you already know?

Scope	Demand for functionality
Comparison	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Suggestions/recommendations for tools and action to bring in line with the global framework ▪ Highlighting strenghts and weaknesses ▪ Quantify the impact of UFBS on the environment, economy, society and ecology
Explanation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Whether or not you get monetized data that makes it easier for people to evaluate ▪ The possibility to identify the gaps/flaws in 'our' city and to direct users to material on how to fix the situation

3.3 Integration

How would you like the results look like so that you can actually use them for planning, supporting decisions, convince residents etc.?

Scope	Demand for integration
Comparison	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Encourage twinning and leader - follower cities ▪ Positive competition, comparison of different aspects/general situation ▪ comparing similar cities and UF-NBS solutions around the globe
Explanation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ All aspects are classified and compared ▪ assessment of qualitative and quantitative indicators in some simple way ▪ Users can continuously feedback to achieve the purpose of continuously optimizing the tool

Synthesis of users' demands for scenario application and benchmarking tool for UF-NBS (Milestone 4.3)

References

IUCN (2020). Global Standard for Nature-based Solutions. A user-friendly framework for the verification, design and scaling up of NbS. First edition. Gland, Switzerland: IUCN.

<https://doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.CH.2020.08.en>.

Scheuer, S., Haase, D., Jache, J., Labohm, B., Sumfleth, L., Wellmann, T., & Wolff, M. (2021). Compiled knowledge repository on UF-NBS based on academic literature review (Deliverable 1.2). H2020 project CLEARING HOUSE, grant no. 821242. <http://review.clearinghouseproject.eu/>.

Thinknature (2019). ThinkNature Nature-Based Solutions Handbook. Edited by Somarakis, G., Stagakis, S., Chrysoulakis, N., Mesimäki, M. & Lehvavirta. European Union.

<https://doi.org/10.26225/jerv-w202>.